

16-positions. This also supports the earlier stereochemical assignment of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid.

The second product (m.p. 203°) was characterised as 3-acetyl-16-keto methyl olean-12-ene-28-oate (III) by direct comparison of m.p., mixed m.p., TLC and IR spectrum with an authentic sample prepared by oxidation of 3-acetyl methyl echinocystate available in our laboratory. The formation of 16-keto compound (III), though in traces, is rather interesting. There may be two alternative explanations; (i) that the diacetate described earlier may contain mainly the 3,15-diacetate and trace of 3,16-diacetate formed by acyl migration during column chromatography, for such acyl migrations are known to occur^{7,8}, (ii) The acyl migration takes place during the process of dehydration. The second process appears to be more probable since the diacetate showed single spot in TLC over silica gel G and also over AgNO₃-impregnated silica gel G plates in various solvent systems. Incidentally it may be pointed out that Djerassi *et al.*⁹ has reported that the 15 α (equatorial) -OH group undergoes easy dehydration to give 15, 16-double bond whereas the dehydration of 15 β (axial) OH group leads to rearranged product (cf. Dumortierigenin).

The conversion of methyl entagenate to 3-acetyl 15-keto methyl olean-12-ene-28-oate (II) together with the earlier data⁴ conclusively proves the structure and stereochemistry of entagenic acid as 3 β , 15 α , 16 α -trihydroxy olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (Ia).

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Chemical Investigations of the leaves of *Calicarpa arborea* (Verbenaceae)

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IN a previous communication¹ we reported the isolation of betulinic acid, baurenol and β -sitosterol from the bark of *Calicarpa arborea*. The isolation of ursolic acid, epilupeol and β -sitosterol from the leaves of the same plant is reported in this paper.

Air dried and powdered leaves of *C. arborea* were exhaustively extracted with hot benzene for 18 hrs. The benzene extract was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction on repeated chromatography over a column of silica gel afforded from benzene-ethylacetate (4:1) eluate an amorphous solid, m. p. 240-245°. It gave positive Leibermann-Burchardt test. It was then esterified with diazomethane and then acetylated (Ac₂O/Py) and then chromatographed over de-activated alumina and finally crystallised from a mixture of CHCl₃-MeOH. The acetate, m. p. 244-47° was identified as acetyl methyl ursolate by comparison (mixed m.p., TLC and I.R.) with an authentic specimen.

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. After a forerun of waxy material, elution with a mixture of petrol-C₆H₆ (7:3) furnished a solid, m.p. 138-42°. This on chromatography over silica gel impregnated with AgNO₃ yielded an amorphous solid, m.p. 145-50°, which could not be crystallised; ν_{max} 3250, 880 cm⁻¹; MS m/e 426 (M⁺), 408 (M-H₂O)⁺, 393 (M-H₂O-CH₃)⁺, 207, 218 (base peak) and 189. It was acetylated and the crude acetate on chromatography followed by crystallisation from CHCl₃-MeOH yielded a crystalline solid, C₃₁H₅₂O₉, m.p. 157-60° (lit.³ m.p. 163°); ν_{max} 1725, 1220 and 880 cm⁻¹; MS m/e 468 (M⁺), 408 (M-AcOH)⁺, 393 (M-CH₃-HOAc)⁺, 249, 218 (base peak) and 189 suggesting its identity with epilupeol⁴. Finally its identity with epi-lupeol was confirmed by comparison (TLC and I.R.) with an authentic specimen⁵.

Further elution of the column with petrol-C₆H₆ (2:3) afforded a solid which on acetylation and crystallisation furnished β -sitosteryl acetate, C₃₁H₅₂O₉, m.p. 126-128° (lit.⁶ m.p. 127-28°), identical (mixed m.p., TLC and I.R.) with an authentic specimen.

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1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-mono arylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thione: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione₂ (0.01 mole) was dissolved in abs. ethanol (20 ml). To it aryl aldehyde (0.01 mole) and piperidine (0.5 ml) were added. The solution was allowed to stand at the room temperature overnight. The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Since on cooling no solid was obtained the gummy mass was treated with few drops of dil. HCl and allowed to stand for some time. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed repeatedly with distilled water and finally crystallised from ethanol. The m. p. and analytical data of the compounds are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of 1-Phenyl-3-Methyl-4-Mono Arylidene-2-Pyrazolin-5-Thione

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IN our previous work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁴ it has been observed that heterocyclic five membered carbonyl compound 5-pyrazolone possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* which is responsible for the fatal blast disease of the rice crop. Further it has been observed that the replacement of the carbonyl oxygen atom by sulphur enhances the fungicidal activity markedly⁴. It has been earlier reported from this laboratory that 4-mono arylidene derivatives of 5-pyrazolone exhibit significant fungicidal activity^{1,5}. The present investigation was taken up with a view to study and compare the fungitoxicity of 4-mono arylidene derivatives of thio pyrazolone with those of the corresponding oxygenated compound. Treatment of 5-pyrazolone with P₂S₅ affords 5-thiopyrazolone⁴ which on condensation with the aryl aldehydes in the presence of ethanol and piperidine gave the mono-4-arylidene derivatives. The formation of this compound has been established from the satisfactory analytical values, insolubility in dil. NaOH and negative test with ethanolic FeCl₃. Ten such compounds thus prepared were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* by the standard method⁶ using spore germination tests at various concentrations. 5-Thiopyrazolone inhibited 81% of spore germination of *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration while its 4-mono arylidene derivatives displayed poor activity against the same pathogen. On comparison of the activity of the 4-mono arylidene derivative of 5-pyrazolone with the corresponding sulphur analogue it was observed that 4-mono arylidene derivative of 5-pyrazolone is more active than the corresponding sulphur analogue.

Sl. No.	R	m. p. (°C)	N(%) Found (Calc.)	S(%) Found (Calc.)
1.	Phenyl	195	10.00 (10.07)	11.48 (11.51)
2.	Fnyl	230 (d)	10.23 (10.44)	12.1 (11.94)
3.	<i>p</i> -anisyl	180	8.92 (9.09)	10.30 (10.38)
4.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ Phenyl	300	13.11 (13.08)	9.78 (9.96)
5.	<i>o</i> -Cl phenyl	198-200	8.91 (8.97)	10.31 (10.25)
6.	<i>p</i> -OH phenyl	175	9.41 (9.52)	10.69 (10.88)
7.	<i>o</i> -OH phenyl	178	9.39 (9.52)	10.72 (10.88)
8.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ phenyl	163	12.94 (13.00)	9.78 (9.90)
9.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ phenyl	250	12.91 (13.00)	9.75 (9.90)
10.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ phenyl	248	12.93 (13.00)	9.81 (9.90)

Yield of the compounds varied between 35-40%.

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